

Influence of N source and level on grain yield and plant characters, Coimbatore, India.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Tillers		Height		Grains (no./Panicle)	Straw yield		Grain yield		N use efficiency	Total soil N at harvest
	no./ m ²	Increase over control (%)	cm	Increase over control (%)		t/ha	Increase over control (%)	t/ha	Increase over control (%)		
Control – no N PU	13	–	25	–	149	5.8	–	1.7	–	–	588
37.5	15	14	28	10	159	6.6	13	3.0	76	35	697
75.0	18	40	29	15	164	8.6	48	3.4	98	23	728
112.5	16	23	29	15	170	9.2	59	4.2	142	22	735
Av	16	25	28	13	164	8.1	40	3.5	105	24	720
USG											
37.5	16	28	29	15	169	8.0	39	3.4	100	46	679
75.0	17	35	30	19	186	8.5	47	3.9	127	29	721
112.5	22	71	33	30	188	8.9	53	4.6	165	25	788
AV	18	44	30	21	181	8.5	47	4.0	131	30	729
1% FPDU											
37.5	15	15	27	7	160	7.4	29	3.5	105	48	658
75.0	16	29	29	14	166	7.5	29	3.8	122	28	693
112.5	18	41	29	17	166	8.7	50	4.3	150	23	149
Av	16	28	28	13	164	7.9	36	3.9	126	29	700
	SED	CD	SED	CD		SED	CD	SED	CD		
Control vs root	0.99	2.0	0.56	1.1		0.6	1.2	0.26	0.5		
Source × level	0.77	1.6	0.43	0.9		0.5	1.0	0.20	0.4		
Source × level	1.33	2.7	ns	–		ns	–	ns	–		

Ammonia volatilization from waterlogged soils of North Bihar

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In flooded alkaline soils, fertilizer N is lost to air as ammonia during the first few weeks of submergence. We measured ammonia volatilization with different N sources. Soil was an alkaline sandy loam Entisol with pH 8.4, 0.34% organic C, 221 kg KMnO₄-N/ha, and 31% free

CaCO₃ Urea, lac-coated urea, neem cake and urea mixed 1:1 with green manure were the N sources. Rajendra Dhan 201 was grown in a flooded field in 20-m² plots. A 1.2-cm-diam × 35-cm-tall cylindrical frame covered with plastic bag was placed between rows of rice plants immediately after N fertilizer was applied. A petri dish filled with 100 ml of 0.1 N H₂SO₄ was suspended inside the frame. At 3-d intervals, the petri dish was emptied and the contents were distilled for NH₃ with MgO in a microkjeldahl apparatus. Volatilization loss was calculated based on area.

N losses through ammonia volatilization varied widely among N sources. After 16 d, the cumulative N loss ranged from 38 to 55 g/20 m². Volatilization loss was lowest for the urea-green manure treatment: 10 to 26% of fertilizer N volatilized within 4 d of application (see table). Rate of loss declined substantially over time. Total or cumulative loss in 16 d was between 20 and 30% with different N sources. Associated analysis of floodwater, soil solution, and wet soil indicated that high floodwater temperature, high HCO₃⁻ soil solution concentration, high soil pH, and high electrical conductivity caused high volatilization losses in North Bihar. ☞

Percent N loss through NH₃ volatilization, North Bihar, India.

Treatment ^a	% loss of N through volatilization at indicated days after fertilizer application						Cumulative loss (%) in 16d
	0-4 d	4-7 d	7-10 d	10-13 d	13-16 d		
Urea split (45 kg N/ha basal + 22.5 kg N/ha at tillering + 22.5 kg N/ha at panicle initiation)	25 15 ^b 12 ^c	1.8 19 1.8	1.9 1.9 0.4	1.3 1.4 0.8	0.3		29
Urea basal (90 kg N/ha)	26	1.2	1.1	1.0	0.3		29
lac-coated urea basal	25	2.5	1.5	1.1	0.2		30
neem cake-coated urea basal	23	3.0	0.6	0.8	0.4		28
Green manure + urea (1:1)	18	1.0	0.6	0.8	0.2		21

^aEach treatment received 45-45 kg PK/ha. ^bLoss after first urea split. ^cLoss after second urea split.

Evaluation of tractor-drawn puddlers and puddling operations

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In Haryana, most farmers with tractors use mounted, spring-loaded cultivators for puddling. Some also use mounted disk harrows. Rotary blade puddlers, rototillers, and power tillers are

unavailable. Tillage with cultivators and disk harrows varies from two to five times. We evaluated the cultivator, disk harrow, and rotary puddler for rice cultivation (see table).

Results indicate that

1. It takes more time to puddle with a disk harrow than with a cultivator or rotary puddler, presumably because the harrow has a higher draft requirement.
2. With only one tilling, a rotary blade puddler decreases infiltration rate most to 15 mm/d.
3. A second tilling with a harrow or cultivator further reduces the infiltration rate. One or two tillings with the rotary blade puddler

Performance of various tractor-drawn puddlers in Kaul, India.

	Cultivator		Paddy disk harrow		Rotary blade puddler		CD 5%
	Single operation	Double operation	Single operation	Double operation	Single operation	Double operation	
Puddling time (h/ha)	2.9	4.9	4.0	6.7	3.6	5.8	
Puddling cost (\$/ha)	17	29	24	40	22	35	
Infiltration rate (mm/d)	19	14	15	8	15	15	
Yield (t/ha)	4.2	4.3	3.9	4.5	3.8	3.9	0.075
Hills/m ²	36.8	36	37	36.2	36.2	36.3	
Panicles/hill	8.5	8.2	8.5	8.8	8.2	8.0	
Grains/panicle	110	113	113	125	112	114	8.5
1000-grain mass (g)	28.5	29.6	28.0	28.3	29.7	30.7	1.8

4. Two cultivator tillings produce an infiltration rate similar to that from one tilling with a rotary blade

5. The twice harrow-puddled field had lowest infiltration and yielded most. ∞

Effect of irrigation scheduling and nitrogen application on rice yield

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We studied the effect of four water regimes and three N levels and their interactions on rice yield (see table). The water regimes were imposed during a dry spell in mid-Sep 1984.

Crop water use was 1294 mm (see figure), of which 32% was used in vegetative phase, 45% in reproductive

Weekly rainfall and rate of water use (mm)

Rate of water use at different rice growth stages, Raipur, India.

Effect of irrigation and applied N levels on rice yield, Raipur, India.

Water regime ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	No N	40 kg/ha	80 kg/ha
T1	2.5	3.2	4.2
T2	2.5	3.3	3.7
T3	2.5	3.3	3.9
T4	2.5	3.3	3.8
CD	5%	1%	
N level significance	0.1	0.2	
Water level not significant	—	—	
Interaction significance	0.2	0.3	

^a T1-T4 received 5 cm irrigation water when groundwater level was at the indicated depth (in parentheses).

phase, and 23% during ripening. Rainfall met crop water demand until the vegetative phase. Five cm of irrigation water was applied when the groundwater table receded to 0 (T1), 10 (T2), 20 (T3), or 30 cm (T4). Total water use was 1294 mm at T1, 1110 at T2, 1067 at T3, and 927 mm at T4. Water regime did not significantly affect yield (see table), suggesting that continuous submergence is not necessary to produce high yield and that water use efficiency may be greater with a period of drainage between irrigations.

T1 with 80 kg N/ha produced significantly higher yields than the other treatment combinations, suggesting the need for continuous submergence at higher N application levels for good crop

response to fertilizer. Lack of submergence during reproductive stage reduced the yield benefits under high N application. N level may be important to rice field water management. ∞

Growth depression of blue-green algae (BGA) in lowland fields on the Godavari Delta

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BGA blooms do not develop in Godavari Delta rice fields even with inoculation (algalization). Some possible reasons for failure, obtained mainly from